

ISic1057

I.Sicily inscription 1057

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2015.01.17

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Acrae

Place of origin (modern)

near Palazzolo Acreide

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palazzolo Acreide, Museo Archeologico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. ἐνθάδε κῆτε πῆξ
2. ὀνόματι Κλωδία
3. νόσ· τελευτᾷ μη ν(ῶν) ι κ(α)λ(άνδαις) Φεβλαρίες
5. μή [τι]ς ἀνύξη(ι)

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492685

EDCS 41300118

EDCS 39102212

PHI 140537

PHI 175475

Bibliography

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